

1 Immune phenotypes associated with Ras pathway inhibition by Mekinist (trametinib).

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8 Citations

9 1. Khan, Z.M., Real, A.M., Marsiglia, W.M., Chow, A., Duffy, M.E., Yerabolu, J.R., Scopton, A.P. and
10 Dar, A.C., 2020. Structural basis for the action of the drug trametinib at KSR-bound MEK. *Nature*,
11 588(7838), pp.509-514.

12 2. Chen, G., McQuade, J.L., Panka, D.J., Hudgens, C.W., Amin-Mansour, A., Mu, X.J., Bahl, S.,
13 Jané-Valbuena, J., Wani, K.M., Reuben, A. and Creasy, C.A., 2016. Clinical, molecular, and immune
14 analysis of dabrafenib-trametinib combination treatment for BRAF inhibitor–refractory metastatic
15 melanoma: a phase 2 clinical trial. *JAMA oncology*, 2(8), pp.1056-1064.

16 3. Puyalto, A., Rodríguez-Remírez, M., López, I., Macaya, I., Guruceaga, E., Olmedo, M.,
17 Vilalta-Lacarra, A., Welch, C., Sandiego, S., Vicent, S. and Valencia, K., 2024. Trametinib sensitizes
18 KRAS-mutant lung adenocarcinoma tumors to PD-1/PD-L1 axis blockade via Id1 downregulation.
19 *Molecular cancer*, 23(1), p.78.

20 4. Choi, H., Deng, J., Li, S., Silk, T., Dong, L., Brea, E.J., Houghton, S., Redmond, D., Zhong, H.,
21 Boiarsky, J. and Akbay, E.A., 2019. Pulsatile MEK inhibition improves anti-tumor immunity and T cell
22 function in murine Kras mutant lung cancer. *Cell reports*, 27(3), pp.806-819.